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MINE-EMI

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**INNOVATIVE EDUCATION FOR
EMERGING MARITIME ISSUES**

Varna 2021

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Conference of Peripheral Maritime Regions

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The international scientific conference "Innovative education for emerging maritime issues" is conducted on 25.02.2021 in the framework of Multiplier event of the project MINE-EMI (Maritime innovative network of education for emerging maritime issues) hosted by Nikola Vaptsarov Naval Academy (NVNA), Varna.

The aim of the conference is to outline the emerging maritime issues that the authors have identified and want to include in the developed master's programs in the framework of the MINE-EMI project – Port and ship operations, Integrated maritime policy and Port and maritime logistic.

The presented materials were discussed and advocated by the conference participants from Marine Cluster Bulgaria, Conference of the Peripheral Maritime Regions and Piraeus Municipality. All the presentations are accepted for publishing in the conference proceedings.

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Unmanned aerial vehicles in port operations - use cases and benefits

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Abstract — The digitalization and progress towards Industry 4.0 is so fast that the manager could easily deviate from the trends providing competitiveness. In the context of the port domain, the aim is to achieve economic efficiency based on safety, security, and a clean environment. The article's aim is in an accessible and effective way to facilitate the reader by building a general idea of the potential of Drone technology in the modern smart port. The article identifies vital port activities and the role of UAVs in them. The approach of Nikola Vaptsarov Naval Academy to master and develop drone technology in the maritime industry is also demonstrated.

Keywords— *Ports, Drones, UAVs, UASs, Port operations, Maritime education, Industry 4.0*

INTRODUCTION

Ports have always been a fundamental condition for communication, expansion, and trade in human civilization's development and life. In general, the port is the interface that ensures the interaction between shipping and other modes of transport. The necessary natural, infrastructural, technological, organizational, and legal aspects are the basis of the algorithm of operation of the port as a system. The modern port manager is obliged to orient quickly and efficiently in modern technologies' potential and diversity. For this purpose, it is essential to clarify "drone" technology's role in the modern port. In the general public and the consumer market, the term "drone" has gained wide popularity and recognition among people, but in the professional literature, more often used is "unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs)" or "unmanned aerial systems (UASs)".

The topic's relevance is implied by the fact that more and more businesses and industries add value to their activities by applying drone technology. The main goals set by the author are the following:

- To present the port as part of the technological progress and Industry 4.0;
- To present the "Drone" technology and its potential to contribute to Industry 4.0;

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- To identify and present crucial port operations;
- To identify and present drone applications in critical port operations.
- To reveal the approach of Nikola Vaptsarov Naval Academy for adapting the UAVs technology;

The author's supporting idea is that UAVs could be part of the modern advanced development of ports. The progression of drone technologies has contributed to their affordability, and the acquisition of aviation UAVs capabilities has become more affordable and cheaper. The possession of the main port elements such as quays, cranes, and warehouses could be very capital-intensive, especially compared to modern UAV purchases.

UAVs APPLICATIONS IN SMART PORTS – INDUSTRY 4.0

The development of electronics and the miniaturization of critical sensors to ensure stable flight has made unmanned aerial vehicles from exotic military and specialized industrial-technological phenomena an affordable tool for the average consumer. Only for one decade, this trend has enabled almost anyone to acquire aviation capabilities in the field of drones as long as they have access to the international electronics market.

The comfortable and cheap access to the consumer market boosts the popularity to such an extent that it generated a legal vacuum. The situation has pressured governments to assess and control the free and indiscriminate drone handling risks by initiating adequate regulatory initiatives. The European Union expressed its approach with the entry into force of two European Union(EU) Commission Delegated Regulation 2019/945[1] and 2019/947[2]. Market forecast expected steady drone market growth, which will double its size within the next five years[3].

Easy access and low cost, on the one hand, allow for easy implementation of the technology, even for personal entertainment use, but on the other hand, this has harmed public safety[4]. The imposed EU rules neutralized the lag of the regulation from drone technology's rapid technological development. The different uses were distinguished based on the level of risk arising from exploitation. On this basis, drones have been divided into three main categories of use for the European Union figure 1.

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Figure 1. European Union categories of UAS operations[1][2].

The approach enables UASs widespread use but based on rules that stimulate their use and development safely and beneficially for society[5]. The "open category "has the lowest operational risk and, accordingly, the lowest requirements for operator's training and certifications, but it must be subject to more significant and stricter operational restrictions. Its scope includes everyone who operates for recreational purposes in visual line of sight(VLOS) below 120 altitudes above the terrain. Drones could be custom made or must meet specific minimal technical requirements. Operations fall within the "specific category" scope when flights need to be operated outside the open category's limits, but the risk is low to moderate. The "certified category" refers to larger drones and flights within controlled airspace. These operations are high risk and must comply with civil aviation requirements.

Figure 2. UAVs as part of the Smart Port Conception[6].

As part of world trade, seaports exist in a competitive environment in which they should quickly catch up and make progress in the adoption of new technologies and industry 4.0 [7]. Modern UAVs have the technological capacity to successfully integrate and contribute to any key technology forming the concept of a modern smart port figure 2[8][6]. Deployment of more modern digital devices gives better brainpower to the process management inside the smart port. Drones have a lot to show and contribute because they are robots flying in the sky and, with their sensors, can obtain a different type of data and send it in real-time.

Hard-to-reach places could easily be safely explored and scanned with a wide variety of on-board sensors. It is a matter of understanding and creatively implementing drone technology to discover all the benefits of their use. Figure 3 reveals some significant benefits arising from their use[6].

UAVs features benefiting industrial applications

- Capture a variety of data from the air
- Share captured information in real time
- Ability to operate in complex and dangerous areas
- Access to remote and hard to reach places
- Autonomous flight capabilities outside the line of sight
- Possibility for interoperability with other systems

Figure 3. UAVs features benefiting industrial applications[6].

UAVs AS PART OF THE PORT SAFETY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

For the implementation of water transport, natural waterways are used without building road infrastructure, as inland transport. At the same time, ports ensure interoperability between ships, trucks, trains, and other means of transport. In this complicated collaboration, participate a diversity of technical means, organizations, and authorities. Within a limited coastal area, the interests of many stakeholders are intertwined.

In order to solve its complex tasks, the port must have a wide variety of facilities that meet the needs of modern shipping and cargo flows:

- navigable waters for maneuvering, moving, and mooring ships;
- marine channels and navigation signs;
- cargo quay berths – terminals with the respective cargo specialization;
- open storage areas;
- close warehouse areas;
- breakwaters and facilities for the protection of the coast;
- sufficient land area and roads for land transport and other specialized equipment;
- Office residential buildings and structures;
- Cargo handling and transport machines;
- and other essential engineering facilities and equipment;

Most of the facilities listed above are large and complex installations and are within the scope of their safety management requirements.

Figure 4 illustrates the main marine activities associated with the port's functionality, and for each of them, it is necessary to develop appropriate procedures[9]. The correct implementation of each of these activities ensures maritime safety and guarantees the reliable arrival, departure, and maneuvering of all ships in the port.

Ports and all related operations continue to be covered by increasing safety, security, and environmental requirements[10]. Statistics support this trend, as the EMSA report on maritime

incidents shows worrying values for 2019 with persistent occurrences for each of the years from 2014 to 2019 [11]. A study based on the processing of 471 accidents in seaports taken from the Major Hazard Incident Data Service (MHIDAS) database reveals that most of them, 51%, resulting from releases that could subsequently escalate into an explosion and fire [12]. Main activity carried out in the port is the transport of cargo, which occurs both at sea through ships' movement and at the territory port area. According to statistics, 65 % of the releases accidents are during transport operations with ocean-going vessels involved[12].

Figure 4. Ports tasks and issues[9].

As an integral part of maritime transport, expressed in the ship-cargo-port system's trinity, ports with their activities fall into the risky industries category. In them, the risk is minimized by introducing a safety management system. It follows the steps of identifying hazards, calculating the risk, and taking measures to neutralize or minimize it in a cost-effective way[9].

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Figure 5. General Hazards in Ports[10]

Figure 5 present the general hazards identified in typical port operation scenario, which usually consists of the following typical steps[10]: 1) Contacting the ship; 2) Pilot boarding; 3) Connecting of tugs; 4) Maneuvering with tugs; 5) Maneuvering for berthing; 6) Berthing and mooring; 7) Cargo loading/unloading; 8) Unberthing; 9) Piloting the vessel out of port; 10) Pilot departure; 11) Outward passage of the vessel.

As a modern cyber-physical system with a flexible design, drones could contribute to every step of typical port operations at increasingly affordable prices. Different air analysis sensors could easily be installed on a single drone carrier. Thermal cameras would be effectively used to detect leakage of harmful and highly flammable substances. UAVs characteristics allow for various uses in the prevention phase as part of the risk management system and the monitoring of already started emergency processes, and in the final stage of identification and assessment of the consequences. Figure 6 shows areas of activities in the port domain in which UAVs as modern cyber-physical systems could significantly increase efficiency and safety[6].

Figure 6. UAVs as Cyber-physical system in PORT DOMAIN[6].

Most port domain incidents result from a ship-to-ship or shore collision[12]. Part of preventing these incidents is the maintenance of proper floating marine equipment – International Association of Marine Aids to Navigation and Lighthouse Authorities (IALA) buoyage system[13]. Moving work crews with buoy inspection vessels is incomparably more expensive than carrying out an autonomous inspection with UAVs figure 7.

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Figure 7. Example of marine buoy inspection with UAVs.

The pre-drone inspection provides transparent feedback on the current situation, and on this basis, resources could be allocated much more efficiently without wasting time.

UAVs AND MARITIME EDUCATION

Due to the still young but booming UAV market, there is not yet massive, and recognizable specific application of UAVs that would give serious added value to many activities, even those of a large industrial area as Ports. Technology is accessible, it gives its new capabilities and implementations in many activities and processes, but it also has its risks. In the implementation process, organizations and businesses must rely on combining profitability with safety and responsible use of UAVs. The full development of the UAV's market has not yet been reached. Institutions and businesses should not wait for its point of maturation and sustainable establishment, but rather to create an environment for introducing and effectively adopting technology in a socially useful and acceptable way.

To master the technology and use it efficiently and safely in the first place, organizations must invest in new research, development, and education of future operators. Otherwise, some factors define the situation as risky:

- Low UAV prices;
- Availability of UAV on the free market;
- The need for a system to control and track the purchased UAVs;
- High risk of accidents due to lack of compulsory training;
- The potential risk of incidents with severe consequences, even fatal ones;
- Lack of a system guarantees training and building a safety culture and risk assessment and management capabilities by all pilots and drone operators.

To cope with all these factors, Nikola Vaptsarov Naval Academy developed and opened an officially new UAV laboratory in September 2019 figure 8.

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Figure 8. Nikola Vaptsarov Naval Academy UAVs laboratory[14].

The laboratory enabled the academy to engage in many new activities and launch new training courses with UAVs. Only appropriate educational initiatives leading to public literacy in the context of UAVs and building an adequate culture of safe operation could achieve harmonious implementation and development of technology in all its possible applications.

CONCLUSION

On the one hand, the article identifies and reveals critical port operations and, on the other hand, the potential of a rapidly growing new unmanned aerial vehicle industry. Drone technology's potential to practically contribute to many operations in ports and especially to achieve a safer, cleaner, and more secure port domain has been revealed. But this untapped capacity poses some risks that could only be addressed through adequate training and a culture of safe operation of UAVs. The author presents Nikola Vaptsarov Naval Academy's approach to implement the technology in the training and maritime industry.

The article is an open and accessible way to reveal the opportunities and directions in which experts could work to develop drone technology to implement the concept of a smart port.

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